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**THE IMPORTANCE OF SURFACE ELECTROMYOGRAPHY IN THE
DIAGNOSIS OF TEMPOROMANDIBULAR JOINT
MUSCULOSKELETAL DYSFUNCTION AND BRUXISM UNDER
ACADEMIC STRESS**

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Abstract

At present, stress plays a significant role in everyday human life. Elevated levels of academic stress and neurotic tension among students may contribute to development of functional disturbances, temporomandibular musculoskeletal dysfunction, and bruxism.

Academic overload, chronic psychoemotional stress, sleep disturbances, and increased anxiety levels are closely associated with excessive activity of masticatory muscles and functional disorders of the temporomandibular joint (TMJ).

Investigation of clinical manifestations in students demonstrates the importance of timely diagnosis and increased clinical attention toward this problem.

Surface electromyography (sEMG) represents a noninvasive and informative diagnostic method that allows evaluation of:

- bioelectrical activity of masticatory muscles;
- muscle coordination;
- asymmetry of muscular contraction;
- hyperactivity associated with parafunctional habits.

Application of sEMG contributes to early detection of muscular dysfunctions and improves diagnostic accuracy in patients with bruxism and temporomandibular disorders developing under conditions of chronic academic stress.

Keywords

Academic stress, bruxism, temporomandibular dysfunction, surface electromyography, masticatory muscles, temporomandibular joint.

Introduction

Currently, stress represents an inseparable component of rapidly developing modern society. Academic stress is closely associated with student life due to increased educational workload, large volumes of information, and the necessity for multitasking. These factors frequently result in disturbances of sleep patterns and increased anxiety levels.

One of the major negative factors among students is excessive use of modern communication technologies and smartphones. This contributes to formation of smartphone addiction, characterized by excessive device usage that disrupts daily functioning, decreases concentration and memory performance, alters eating behavior, and negatively affects sleep quality [10].

As a consequence of emotional instability and chronic psychoemotional tension, involuntary muscular contractions and increased muscle tone frequently occur, affecting the entire organism and subsequently contributing to dysfunction of the temporomandibular joint (TMJ) and development of bruxism.

Musculoskeletal Dysfunction of the Temporomandibular Joint

Musculoskeletal dysfunction (MSD) represents impairment of coordinated function of the masticatory muscles and TMJ, commonly associated with occlusal disturbances [2].

Clinically, this pathological process may manifest as:

- clicking within the joint;
- excessive or limited mandibular mobility;
- pain in the TMJ region;
- zigzag mandibular movements during mouth opening;

- development of trigger points within craniofacial muscles.

Bruxism

Bruxism is characterized by involuntary, nonfunctional contractions of the masticatory muscles unrelated to physiological chewing or speech activity.

Tooth clenching during bruxism disrupts the physiological resting position of the mandible due to tonic hyperactivity of elevator muscles [5].

Bruxism contributes to:

- generalized pathological tooth wear;
- functional overload of periodontal tissues;
- gingival recession;
- hypertrophy of masticatory muscles;
- temporomandibular pain dysfunction;
- increased dental sensitivity.

Common clinical complaints in patients with bruxism include:

- morning headaches;
- discomfort after sleep in the jaw, neck, shoulder, and back regions;
- pain during mastication;
- mandibular numbness after awakening;
- clicking within the TMJ;
- dizziness;
- anxiety;
- depressive symptoms;
- appetite disturbances;
- insomnia or restless sleep;
- fractures of restorations and ceramic prosthetic constructions [3].

Among students, many of these symptoms may initially be interpreted as physiological features of young age, resulting in delayed diagnosis and prolonged chronic progression of dysfunction. Therefore, early diagnosis and timely treatment of TMJ musculoskeletal dysfunction and bruxism are highly relevant in contemporary clinical practice.

Surface Electromyography

One of the most informative noninvasive diagnostic methods for evaluating the condition of masticatory muscles is surface electromyography (sEMG).

Based on analysis of obtained data, sEMG allows assessment of:

- functional condition of masticatory musculature;
- level of muscular tension;
- muscular coordination and symmetry [9].

Aim of the Study

To determine the diagnostic significance of surface electromyography of masticatory muscles in students with temporomandibular musculoskeletal dysfunction and bruxism, and to analyze correlations between these findings and levels of neuroticism.

Materials and Methods

The investigation was conducted among fourth- and fifth-year dental students and included 124 participants:

- 80 fourth-year students;
- 44 fifth-year students.

Among fifth-year students, two groups were formed and combined into one main clinical group consisting of 20 participants.

The mean age of examined individuals ranged from 20 to 23 years.

The level of neuroticism was assessed using:

- the Wasserman neuroticism questionnaire;
- the Zung depression scale.

Clinical examination included:

- collection of medical history;
- examination of the maxillofacial region;
- evaluation of facial configuration and symmetry;
- palpation of masticatory and cervical musculature;
- measurement of mouth opening;
- assessment of mandibular deviation during opening movements;

- evaluation of central and functional occlusion;
- assessment of gingival recession severity.

Electromyographic Examination

Registration of bioelectrical potentials of masticatory muscles was performed using a computerized electromyographic analyzer “Synapsis” (NMF “Neurotech”).

Bilateral recording was performed on:

- the masseter muscles;
- the temporalis muscles.

Surface bioadhesive electrodes were positioned on areas of maximal muscular tension identified by palpation.

Electromyographic amplitude values were recorded in microvolts (μV) during two functional tests:

1. physiological resting state;
2. maximal voluntary contraction during tooth clenching.

Results and Discussion

To assess the psychoemotional status of students, neuroticism was evaluated using the Wasserman method, while depressive symptoms were assessed using the Zung depression scale. The obtained results are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1. Wasserman Neuroticism Assessment

Neuroticism Level	4th Year	5th Year	Total %
0–12 points — low neuroticism or absence of neurotic manifestations	21 student s	13 student s	28%
13–28 points — moderate neuroticism	32 student s	21 student s	43%

Neuroticism Level	4th Year	5th Year	Total %
29–40 points — high neuroticism	27 students	10 students	29%

Table 2. Zung Depression Scale

Depression Level	4th Year	5th Year	Total %
20–59 points — normal psychological condition	74 students	33 students	86%
60–69 points — moderate depression	6 students	9 students	12%
≥70 points — severe depression	—	2 students	2%

According to the obtained data, students were divided into three groups depending on results of psychoemotional testing.

The investigation demonstrated:

- low neuroticism in 28% of students;
- moderate neuroticism in 43%;
- high neuroticism in 29%.

Analysis using the Zung scale suggested:

- severe depression in 2% of participants;
- moderate depression in 12%;
- absence of depressive symptoms in 86%.

Following analytical evaluation, 20 fifth-year dental students underwent detailed clinical examination.

Clinical Findings

Among the 20 examined students:

- 12 complained of pain and tension in the cervical and masticatory muscles;

- 2 reported pain during mastication;
- several students noted rapid muscular fatigue;
- morning pain after awakening and daytime headaches were frequently reported.

Clinical examination revealed:

- mild facial asymmetry;
- mandibular deviation in 4 participants;
- pain during palpation of medial pterygoid muscles in 6 students;
- hypertonicity of masticatory musculature in 10 students.

In 12 students, clicking and crepitation within the temporomandibular joint were observed during mandibular movements despite preservation of full mouth opening amplitude.

Fifteen students demonstrated zigzag mandibular displacement during slow mouth opening.

Two participants exhibited parafunctional alterations of facial musculature manifested by the “thimble symptom” associated with absence of anterior open bite and infantile swallowing patterns.

Oral Examination Findings

Intraoral examination demonstrated:

- generalized gingival recession in 15 students;
- wedge-shaped cervical defects in 3 students;
- generalized pathological tooth wear in 10 students.

Pathological tooth wear was associated with chronic involuntary mandibular compression and forced occlusal position.

Occlusal disturbances identified included:

- dysfunction of functional occlusion;
- anterior occlusal disturbances;
- lateral occlusal interferences.

Supercontacts were identified in 6 students.

Electromyographic Findings

Results of surface electromyographic examination of the masseter and temporalis muscles in resting conditions and during functional loading are presented in Table 3.

Previously established normative values of masticatory muscle biopotentials were used as reference standards [4].

Table 3. Functional Characteristics of Masseter and Temporalis Muscles

Muscle Group	Right Side at Rest (μV)	Right Side During Load (μV)	Left Side at Rest (μV)	Left Side During Load (μV)
Masseter muscle	98.4 \pm 12.3	740 \pm 16.0	101.7 \pm 12.3	789 \pm 16.0
Temporalis muscle	86.2 \pm 1.0	968.4 \pm 16.0	84.4 \pm 16.3	980.8 \pm 16.0

The obtained electromyographic data demonstrated increased bioelectrical activity of the masticatory and temporalis muscles during functional loading, indicating muscular hyperactivity associated with bruxism and temporomandibular dysfunction under academic stress conditions.

Comparative Electromyographic Analysis

Reference electromyographic values according to L.P. Gerasimova (2013) demonstrated substantially lower amplitudes of masticatory and temporalis muscle activity compared with the clinical group examined in the present investigation.

Reference EMG Values (L.P. Gerasimova, 2013)

Muscle	Rest (μV)	Functional Load (μV)
Masseter muscle	32.3 \pm 2.1	360 \pm 20.0
Temporalis muscle	24.0	385.0 \pm 21.0

According to electromyographic findings, 100% of examined students demonstrated significant elevation of mean bioelectrical amplitude of the masticatory muscles, indicating compensatory hyperactivity of the masticatory musculature.

Based on comprehensive clinical examination, a preliminary diagnosis of temporomandibular musculoskeletal dysfunction and bruxism was established in 15 students, corresponding to 75% of the examined clinical group.

Conclusion

Among students of Bashkir State Medical University, moderate and high levels of neuroticism were identified, while 2% of participants demonstrated signs of severe depression according to psychological testing results.

Surface electromyographic examination revealed increased average bioelectrical amplitude of masticatory muscles in all examined individuals.

The high prevalence of neuroticism combined with elevated frequency of temporomandibular dysfunction and bruxism among students indicates a strong relationship between psychoemotional stress and dysfunction of the stomatognathic system.

The obtained results emphasize:

- the necessity for early diagnosis of bruxism and TMJ dysfunction;
- the importance of psychoemotional assessment in students;
- the diagnostic value of surface electromyography;
- the need for development of multidisciplinary preventive and therapeutic algorithms.

References

1. Wolf GF, Rateitschak EM, Rateitschak KH. Periodontology. Moscow: MEDpress-inform; 2008. 548 p.
2. Orlova OR, Konovalova ZN, Alekseeva AYU, et al. Relationship between bruxism and pain dysfunction of the temporomandibular joint. RMJ. 2017;25(24):1760–1763.

3. Orekhova LYu, Farkhshatova RR, Gerasimova LP, et al. In vitro analysis of proliferative activity of cells on collagen membranes for regeneration of oral soft tissues. *Medical Bulletin of Bashkortostan*. 2019;14(5):35–42.
4. Gerasimova LP. Investigation of the functional state of the masseter and temporalis muscles in temporomandibular dysfunction using electromyography. *Science in Central Russia*. 2013;4S:178–181.
5. Gerasimova LP, Khaibullina RR, Gilmutdinova LT. Physiotherapeutic technologies in rehabilitation of patients with chronic generalized periodontitis and bruxism. *Medicine*. 2015;1:56–58.
6. Ulitovsky SB, Shevtsov AV. Study of periodontal disease prevalence in orthodontic patients. *Periodontology*. 2020;25(1):37–41.
7. Orekhova LYu, Kudryavtseva TV, Loboda ES, Neyzberg DM. Cause-and-effect relationship of gingival recession development and antibacterial/anti-inflammatory approaches in prevention and treatment. *Periodontology*. 2017;4(85):20–23.
8. Marzena D, Tomasz G. New perspectives in the diagnostic of gingival recession. *Adv Clin Exp Med*. 2014;23:857–863.
9. Makedonova YuA, Yarygina EN, Aleksandrov AV, Chizhikova TV, Devyatchenko YuA, Filimonova ON. Grading of masticatory muscle hypertonicity severity. *Endodontics Today*. 2024;22(1):80–85. DOI: 10.36377/ET-0006.
10. Derevensky JL, Hayman V, Gilbeau L. Behavioral addictions: excessive gambling, gaming, internet, and smartphone use among children and adolescents. *Pediatr Clin North Am*. 2019;66(6):1163–1182. DOI: 10.1016/j.pcl.2019.08.008.
11. De Molon RS, de Avila ED, de Souza JA, Nogueira AV, Cirelli CC, Cirelli JA. Combination of orthodontic movement and periodontal therapy for full root coverage in a Miller class III recession: a case report with 12 years of follow-up. *Braz Dent J*. 2012;23(6):758–763.

12. Zucchelli G, Mounssif I. Periodontal plastic surgery. *Periodontol* 2000. 2014;68(1):333–368.